

Писарева Г.А.

Нижегород, НИУ ВШЭ – Нижний Новгород

**FOREIGN LANGUAGE CAPACITY IMPACT
IN THE RUSSIAN LABOUR MARKET:
ESTIMATION, FACTORS AND INDUSTRIAL PECULIARITY**

In the modern realities, the interest in the issue of foreign language (FL) learning has been rising, especially under in the context of globalization and intercultural integration [1]. The ability to speak foreign languages is seen as a part of human capital that increases efficiency and productivity of workers [2]. More and more employers pay attention to the foreign language knowledge under the business internalization conditions. Does the rising interest in the FL skills pay off?

Foreign language wage premium can be understood as additional payment for the possession of foreign language skills.

Objective

The objective of this paper is to receive a quantitative estimation of the impact of foreign language skills on wages in the Russian labour market depending on a number of factors. Those factors are age, gender, education experience, region type, occupational sector.

To accomplish the objective, we first conduct literature review, then develop an empirical part. The latter consists of the model construction and the interview.

Statistical part: data and methodology

In the statistical part, we develop a model and estimate it using OLS methodology. We use certain instruments to capture the variables that cannot be observed and measured (e.g firm size is used as a proxy for marginal labour productivity [3]). We also limit our sample to employed people of the age of 27+ as an attempt to avoid the possible endogeneity problem between education and wages since it is not only education that influences wages, but also vice versa[4]. By the age of 27 one has already completed their education (in our sample the maximum education duration is 20 years; on average, one starts their education path at the age of 7; given that, we assume that 27-year-olds-plus are expected, on average, to have their education process completed. Almost the same reasoning is used to escape the endogeneity issue between FL knowledge and wages (FL yields a wage premium; higher salary allows to learn FL). To overcome the problem, we restrict the sample to those only who answered the question on whether they were learning some professional courses during the previous year negatively.

The research is carried out on the data from 28th round of RLMS HSE (2019).

Statistical part: the model

Following [4], we estimate wage premium in the model below:

$$\ln(\text{wage})_i = \alpha + x'_i\beta + z'_i\gamma + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

In (1), x'_i is the i -th row of the matrix with variables related to the language premium estimation, z'_i is the i -th row of matrix with control and theoretical variables, which are not related to the language premium. ε_i is the disturbance term, i.i.d. $N(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$.

Model (1) is based on labour demand curve. The latter is derived from the producer optimization problem solution.

In order to measure the language premium for people of different ages, we divided them into 5 groups: age 27-30, age 30-40, age 40-50, age 50-60 and age 60+.

Statistical part: results and discussion

The basic model is estimated for women of age 27-30, living in a city and working in financial sector. Under these circumstances, the FL wage premium is, on average, 26,8%. There is no gender effect registered, although men are estimated to get higher salary than women, on average.

Higher education is calculated to bring certain benefits in the sense of higher wages: tertiary education provides 24,2% higher salary, on average, than post-secondary education. There is also a language premium in post-secondary education: average wages of those with FL skills are 14% higher than of those with no such skills.

The following results were received for the region impact on wages and language premium: people living in regional centers get 19% higher salary in comparison to those who live in cities, and the centers are estimated to provide 11.8% higher wages for those who know a FL in comparison to those who does not.

The most significant FL wage premium is estimated for the sector of finance (26,8% in the basic model). In the education sector, the premium is much less (3,6%), while in the sector of trade it is even negative (-0,5%). Rather surprising results were received in the FL wage estimation for the sectors of science (-3%), operating controls (-1,7%) and construction (-7,6%). Negative FL premium is estimated for engineering (-12%), agriculture (-15,6%), chemical industry (-26,5%), church (-26,6%) and some other sectors.

However, these results are received for young people only (27-30 years). It was estimated that older people tend to get higher salary: 30-40-year-olds get

13,8% more than 27-30, 40-50 – 22% more, 50-60 – 23.5% more, and 60+ get 26,6% more as a wage premium.

The model (1.2) estimation results are (partly) presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Model (1) estimation results

Variable	Coefficient value
constant	8,942*** [0,188]
FL skills	0,268** [0,128]
post-secondary education*FL skills	0,140*** [0,052]
gender	0,326*** [0,020]
regional center*FL skills	-0,150*** [0,052]
engineering*FL skills	-0,388** [0,198]
construction*FL skills	-0,344** [0,149]
agriculture*FL skills	-0,424** [0,205]
operating controls*FL skills	-0,285* [0,157]
education*FL skills	-0,232* [0,119]
science*FL skills	-0,298** [0,149]
trade*FL skills	-0,273** [0,122]
church*FL skills	-0,534*** [0,156]
chemical industry*FL skills	-0,533*** [0,181]
FL skills * age 30–40	0,138* [0,075]
FL skills * age 40–50	0,220*** [0,078]

End of Table 1

FL skills * age 50–60	0,235*** [0,090]
FL skills * age 60+	0,266** [0,115]
Number of observations	3970
R-squared	0,359
F-statistic	26,802***

Note: standard errors are in brackets [] (heteroscedasticity consistent); *: p-value < 0.1, **: p-value < 0.05, ***: p-value < 0.01.

Interview part

The interview part consists of two interviews with consulting companies: KPMG (since 8th June, 2022 — Kept in Russia) and SBS Consulting (the interviews were conducted in 2022). Members of both companies were asked a list of questions on FL policy.

High command of English is required in both companies (B2 level and higher). Other foreign languages knowledge is welcome but not paid off. In KPMG, though, non-English foreign speakers can be needed in certain top positions. English is used as a part of corporate culture in KPMG and SBS Consulting. There is no direct FL premium in either company, though there can be indirect effect of FL skills on wages in the sense of better promotion chances.

Conclusions

The key results of the paper are as follows. There is a FL wage premium in Russian labour market, and it depends on such factors as age, education, occupation, region type. The premium is the same for male and female, though. In the basic regression, the premium is 26,8%. There has been revealed negative wage premium in certain manufacture sectors.

FL policies in KPMG and SBS Consulting are similar in the sense of a high command of English required and the career prospects for those with good FL skills.

References:

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